

HEAppE Middleware: From desktop to HPC

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Abstract. HEAppE Middleware is IT4Innovations' in-house implementation of HPC-as-a-Service concept. It is being continuously developed for a more than a 10 years taking into account the user requirements and security policies and constraints of different HPC or Data centres while supporting a number of widely used HPC workload managers. Via simple and easy-to-use REST API the end-users can manage the complete HPC job life cycle, file transfers, and HEAppE-specific functionality. HEAppE provides a user-friendly, secure, and cost-effective solution for the end-users or third-party applications on how to remotely access supercomputing resources without the HPC-specific know-how.

Keywords: HEAppE Middleware · HPC-as-a-Service · High-Performance Computing · Remote Execution · Secure Access

1 Introduction

HPC-as-a-Service concept is well know term in the domain of High-Performance Computing. It offers remote access to supercomputing infrastructure in a service-like manner offering HPC capabilities to users or third party applications and services while encapsulating most of the HPC specific functionality behind an easy-to-use interface.

IT4Innovations also adopted this approach more than 10 years ago when it was apparent that there is a growing community of users that wants to integrate HPC capabilities in their own solutions or just need a simple interface to utilize the power of supercomputers within their specific domains.

Throughout its existence HEAppE Middleware ¹ was successfully integrated into a number of national and international projects [3] under the header of Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, and European Space Agency projects and many others and also deployed at several major HPC infrastructure or data centre providers.

2 From desktop to HPC

This chapter describes the HEAppE's basic features and focuses mainly on the latest version enabling the users to test HEAppE in a simulated cluster envi-

¹ <https://heappe.eu>

ronment on their own local computer. For more technical details, see the official HEAppE documentation².

Main features and security

HEAppE Middleware implements several concepts in terms of remote and secure access to computational resources. In terms of security, HEAppE recognizes two types of credentials: *external user accounts* and *internal service accounts*. External user accounts do not have direct access to the HPC infrastructure itself. They are used only to authenticate the external user via HEAppE middleware to access only HEAppE's provided functions via its REST API.

Service accounts are used to submit jobs to the actual HPC cluster queue. These service accounts are usually non-personalized standard cluster accounts bound to a specific computational project. The service accounts are generated specifically to be used within HEAppE Middleware on the request of *Primary Investigator (PI)* of a given computational project. This way the PI of the project agrees with the creation of service accounts and their usage within HEAppE.

HEAppE provides the mapping between an external user accounts and internal service accounts. It keeps track of which service account was used for the submission of which compute job and which user made the job submission.

HEAppE also enables the users to run only a pre-prepared set of so-called *Command Templates*. Each template defines a script or executable binary, that will be executed on the cluster together with any dependencies or third-party software it might require.

Simulated HPC cluster environment

The simulated HPC cluster feature within the HEAppE Middleware allows users to create a virtual representation of an HPC environment directly on their computer. This *simulated cluster* runs in a Docker container, leveraging containerization technology for easy deployment and management.

With the simulated HPC cluster running on a Docker container, users can establish a *self-contained and regulated environment* on their personal computer. This eliminates the necessity for dedicated physical infrastructure or remote access to an HPC system for development purposes. Users can set up and configure the simulated cluster on their local machine, allowing them to efficiently test and experiment with HPC workflows through the HEAppE's REST API in the *sandbox mode*.

Users have the ability to manage jobs by creating, submitting, monitoring, cancelling, and deleting them on the simulated HPC cluster. Job specifications, such as the number of tasks, task dependencies, and job arrays, can be defined to simulate real-world HPC job scenarios.

² <https://heappe.it4i.cz/docs>

After completing the testing of HEAppE on the simulated HPC cluster, it is straightforward to change the configuration and start using HEAppE in the same way, but with the difference that HPC computational jobs will be executed on a real HPC infrastructure.

3 Summary and HEAppE's showcases

This chapter contains a list of the most important projects where HEAppE has been integrated as an integral part of the developed solution. Infrastructures' list illustrates that HEAppE Middleware is mature enough to be adopted also by other HPC infrastructure providers apart of IT4Innovations' HPC systems.

Projects and use-cases

- **DHI**: First version of HPC-as-a-Service Middleware; Integration of HPC into hydrological domain. <https://www.mikepoweredbydhi.com>
- **Floreon**: FLOod REcognition On the Net; Web-based map interface integrating data visualizations and HPC on-demand analysis from different thematic domains [4]. <https://www.floreon.eu>
- **UrbanTEP**: Urban Thematic Exploitation Platform; ESA funded TEP platform providing data hosting and data processing services from the area of urbanisation [2]. <https://urban-tep.eu>
- **LEXIS Platform**: Large-scale EXecution for Industry and Society; H2020 project that is building an advanced engineering platform at the confluence of HPC, Cloud and Big Data. <https://lexis-project.eu>
- **Fiji**: Fiji is an open source image processing package based on ImageJ2; Plugin for Fiji to access HPC for advance image processing. <https://imagej.net/plugins/hpc-workflow-manager>
- **LIGATE**: H2020 Drug discovery solutions for HPC; Urgent computing workflows for drug discovery. <https://www.ligateproject.eu>
- **EVEREST**: H2020 dEsign enVironmEnt foR Extreme-Scale big data analyTics on heterogeneous platforms; HEAppE execution workflows via LEXIS platform running at IBM infrastructure. <https://everest-h2020.eu/>
- **BLENNED**: BLockchain Enabled Deep learning Data analysis; ESA funded project created a peer-to-peer deep learning training platform for decentralised processing [1].
- **BioDT**: Biodiversity Digital Twin for Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Prediction Capabilities; Horizon Europe project creating the Biodiversity Digital Twin. <https://biodt.eu>

Infrastructures

- **LRZ**: Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (DE); HEAppE used to integrate LRZ's HPC systems into the LEXIS platform. <https://www.lrz.de>

- **EPCC**: Centre of Excellence at the University of Edinburgh; Providing access to EPCC’s Cirrus cluster for LEXIS platform. <https://www.epcc.ed.ac.uk>
- **IBM**: IBM HPC solutions; HEAppE is used to access IBM’s cluster in the scope of H2020 EVEREST project.
- **CINECA**: Operating the largest computing centre in Italy; HEAppE deployment under preparation to integrate selected CINECA clusters to be utilized in H2020 LIGATE project. <https://www.cineca.it>
- **LUMI**: One of the pan-European pre-exascale supercomputers under the head of EuroHPC JU. HEAppE deployment under preparation as part of BioDT project. <https://lumi-supercomputer.eu>

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